

MS11 Value chain data on nutritional values, waste, added value and resilience collected for 5 case study value chains

Lead Beneficiary: University of Galway

Milestone Description & Contributors

- **Due date:** 31/12/2023
- **Actual submission date:** 20/12/2023
- **Project start date:** September 1st 2021
- **Duration:** 48 months
- **Work package:** WP4
- **Work package leader:** UG
- **Milestone Title:** Value chain data on nutritional values, waste, added value and resilience collected for 5 case study value chains
- **Means of Verification**

Data set complete and ready to integrated into the LCA.

1. Milestone description

Each case study value chain has specific characteristics in terms of nutritional output, waste generated, value added and resilience. These attributes are important for benchmarking wider sustainability. Information pertinent to these attributes must be collected in advance of the full RADIANT-Metrics assessment. This milestone represents the compilation of basic attribute information for the five case study value chains, as preparation for the full RADIANT-Metrics (quantitative) assessment.

2. Means of Verification

Have you provided the Mean of Verification described in the GA? Yes

The means of verification is the provision of a dataset that lists the main attributes for five AURORA value chains. The first draft of this small dataset is copied into this report (below). At this stage, values remain descriptive and semi-quantitative, until full analysis is undertaken using the prototype RADIANT-Metrics framework.

Value chain	Location	Description	Main output (value chain)	Possible secondary functional outputs	Nutritional value	Added value	Waste	Resilience
Leafy greens direct marketing	Azores (Portugal)	Agroecological production of a salad mix made of lettuce, swisschard (Beta vulgaris subsp. vulgaris), golden purslane (Portulaca oleracea), garden orache (Atriplex hortensis), buck's-horn plantain (Plantago coronopus), and ten mustard plants	Salad mix (lettuce, Swiss Chard, Mustards, Buckhorn (UC), Atriplex Red (UC), Tatsoi, Purslane (UC))	Resilience & regulatory ecosystem services; higher value-added at point of primary production (€ per ha); possibly higher nutrient density unit	Higher vs lettuce benchmark – values TBC	Average. More diverse nutritional mix and higher resilience vs lettuce benchmark, but no processing value-added.	Low up to point of sale (direct marketing). Estimated 20%	Higher vs lettuce benchmark (deeper roots, some nitrogen fixing, adequate water supply and high OM inputs to soil)

		from the Brassica genus, such as tatsoi (Brassica rapa)						
Bere barley flour	Orkney islands (UK)	Production of bere barley as a UC in an agroecological approach, with legume intercropping.	Flour	Resilience & regulatory ecosystem services.	Average. Little evidence of different flour composition.	Moderate at point of sale.	Average. Similar value chains to conventional barley. Estimated 15%	Higher vs typical barley varieties as benchmark. Better adapted to windy climate. Agroecological cultivation with fertilisation through legume intercropping.
Acorn	Portugal	Harvest of acorns as a UC after the pigs have fed on them, in a Montado system (agro-silvo-pastoral system)	Acorn flour, Acorn meat substitute, & Bellota pork	Resilience & regulatory ecosystem services; higher value-added at point of primary	High. Alternative protein (low fat, high fibre); alternative flour gluten-free and high in oils (& amino acids.	High. Premium products, includes processing of acorns into meat substitutes.	Low. High value products with little wastage after harvesting. Estimated 10%	High. Multiple high value products (diversification). Production cost of pork less subject to international feed price.

				production (€ per ha); possibly higher nutrient density unit (flour)				
Hunter barley beer direct marketing	Ireland	On-site production of craft beer from heritage variety (Hunter) barley as a UC. Direct marketing to consumers via courier and postal sales.	Packaged beer	Resilience and ecosystem services from heritage barley.	Low (alcoholic beverage)	Higher share of sale price to farm/brewery. Adding value to barley by selling beer rather than grain.	Low. Packaged on farm & sold direct. Estimated 5%.	High. Flexible operations can vary output and change between grain or beer sales. Some evidence of improved drought resistance for Hunter barley vs conventional varieties.
Vegetables	France	Approx. 150 varieties, mostly landraces and unregistered varieties	Vegetable & seed mixes	Resilience & regulatory ecosystem services; higher	Higher vs conventional vegetable production mix benchmark	Moderate at point of sale. No processing value	Low up to point of sale. Estimated 20%.	Higher than conventional cropping owing to direct sales and greater diversity.

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				value-added at point of primary production (€ per ha); possibly higher nutrition density		added, but direct sales		
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